

Learning Strategies for Successful and Unsuccessful University Students.

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Abstract

Learning strategies are one of the key factors in achieving success in academic life. Learning strategies were accepted as an individual's choice or approach to managing a task. The purpose of this study was to identify the learning strategies of successful undergraduate students. Toward this purpose, a 14-question survey was designed and administered to a sample of 50 undergraduate students. The research analysis shows that successful students use mostly the same learning strategies, such as metacognition, elaboration, and cognitive learning strategies.

Key words: learning strategies, metacognition, elaboration, cognitive, learning strategies.

Introduction

With reference to the Longman Advanced American Dictionary, the term "learning" refers to information obtained by reading and studying, and a "strategy" is a carefully thought-out plan of action to accomplish a goal. (2007, p. 908, p. Rifqi (2017) summarizes that those students, who are conscious of their own learning and thought processes are said to be practicing metacognition. According to Schumaker and Deshler (2006), as cited in Protheroe (2008), a learning strategy is "an individual's approach to a task. It includes how a person thinks and acts when planning, executing, and evaluating performance on a task and its outcomes. Deshler (2006) is cited by Protheroe (2008) it's said that learning is often done unconsciously, using

various strategies to organize and remember information. According to researchers Wang, Haertel, and Walberg (1993–1994), presented by Protheroe (2008), a student's aptitude, particularly metacognitive processes, had the most significant impact on learning and suggested that teaching how to use learning strategies strengthens students' metacognitive abilities, leading to improvement in learning.

Weinstein and Mayer (1986) state that elaboration strategies are essential for various learning tasks, including basic tasks like forming mental images or sentences, as well as complex tasks like paraphrasing and summarizing; organizational strategies are used for basic tasks like grouping or ordering items, while complex tasks involve outlining passages or creating hierarchy; comprehension monitoring strategies check understanding of material, using self-questioning to guide comprehension; and affective strategies help overcome test anxiety by reducing external distractions and directing attention away from the test. In order to achieve success, students should practice different types of learning strategies.

In addition, Simsek (2010) mentions that learning strategies are crucial in education, as they help assess and accommodate individual student learning styles. The spectrum of learning strategies expands from simple repetition to the internal motivation of learners. According to Weinstein and Mayer (1986), learning strategies are classified into five major groups (Balaban and Simsek 2010). These groups include strategies of rehearsal, elaboration, organization, metacognition, and motivation. Simsek (2006) states that rehearsal involves repeating important material, while elaboration extends content with additional information; organization involves reviewing and restructuring material; metacognition involves self-awareness and self-criticism; and motivational strategies involve students' perceptions and conscious efforts to perform better. Weinstein (1987) suggested that students should be trained to develop an understanding of and skills for using appropriate strategies that satisfy their needs.

It is believed that learning techniques are deliberate, free acts that a student does to accomplish a specific aim. The student's perceived capacity as well as other individual elements like willingness to learn and, most importantly, the perception

of the efficacy of using learning techniques are major determinants of the usage of self-regulating learning strategies. Garcia & Tejedor (2017) say that students are required to use specific learning strategies, some of which are intentional, in order to support autonomous learning and enhance their academic performance (Alarcón et. al., 2019). Additionally, Herrera & Lorenzo (2009), state that the student is the primary emphasis of higher education, and as such, academic institutions should address the cognitive, socio-affective, and motivational aspects of learning (Alarcón et. al. 2019). Pintrich and García (1993) identify three primary categories of learning strategies: cognitive techniques focused on the development of critical thinking skills and the evaluation, elaboration, and organization of knowledge; resource regulation techniques; and metacognitive methods, which involve organizing, planning, and reviewing activities taken during the learning process and describe how the student divides up his or her time and space to study, plan, build peer learning, and ask for assistance when needed (Alarcón et. al. 2019).

According to Weinstein and Mayer (1986), as stated in Farzaneh Motamedi (2017), elaboration strategies can be used in various ways, such as creating analogies, paraphrasing, summarizing, transforming information into another form, applying new information, directly relating prior knowledge, using comparison and contrast methods, drawing inferences or conclusions, and teaching what we are learning to others. However, the specific method a student uses is not critical to success. A good repertoire of elaboration strategies helps students perform a wide spectrum of tasks, providing both fluency and flexibility.

There are also other benefits to actively involve students in the learning process, including establishing strong connections between students and increasing motivation and engagement. Motamedi et. al. (2017) indicated that when students employ more strategies, they are likely to be more successful.

Research Methodology

The methodology was based on the application of a qualitative and quantitative approach. The purpose of this research is to find out what learning strategies successful and not-successful university students use. The questionnaire was

designed based on Weinstein's article (1986). Using Weinstein and Mayer's (1986) categorization, a Likert-type scale was created to evaluate university students' learning processes. The survey was taken in an online form by English department students. A group of fifty undergraduate students participated in a survey.

Results

The participants of this study were 50 undergraduate students in the English department (female 75%, male 25%). 13 females are scored A/A+, 15 B/B+, 7 C/D, and 1 F, whereas 6 males are A/A+ takers, 1 B/B+, and 5 C/D. The results reveal that 19 out of 50 students scored A/A+ the previous semester. According to the results, 11 out of 19 successful students usually use metacognition strategies, stating that they carry out activities that are easier for them to handle first. Whereas 5 out of 30 unsuccessful students usually use metacognition strategies. In addition, elaboration strategies such as creating analogies or paraphrasing information are usually used by successful students.

The results showed that rehearsal strategies such as repeating the names of the items in an ordered list were used by nine successful students out of 19. Cognitive learning strategies were preferred by 11 successful students, while 7 unsuccessful students determined that they usually cluster or categorize information. The self-regulating strategy of taking notes and reviewing them was reported to be used by 10 successful students.

How often do you use resources that you used before new assignments?

	Often	Usually	Sometimes	Never	No Answer
A/A+(5)	3	9	7		
B/B+(4)	3	10	2	1	1
C/D(3)	7	4	1		
F(2)	1				

Table 1

The responses to the question "How often do you use resources that you used before for new assignments?" indicated that 25 of the successful students mentioned that

they use resources, and 7 of them use them sometimes, whereas 12 of the unsuccessful students say that they use resources.

How often do you create analogies or paraphrase or summarize information into your own words?

	Often	Usually	Sometimes	Never	No Answer
A/A+(5)	5	10	3	1	
B/B+(4)	6	4	6	6	
C/D(3)	8	1	5		

Table 2

18 out of 19 successful respondents indicated that they summarize or paraphrase information into their own words, something that unsuccessful students do less of. A smaller number of successful respondents have indicated that they often check for comprehension. To the question related to group work, successful students reported that they are usually good at working in groups. The research findings illustrated that successful students usually categorize information, often ask for help from others, and the vast majority of the successful students take notes during the lectures. For the last question, "What learning strategies do you use?" 12 successful students have mentioned that they try to get to know professors and teaching assistants and prefer completing assignments on time. Alternatively, six of the unsuccessful students reported that getting to know professors and teaching assistants is significant, and nine of them indicated that they try to complete assignments on time.

Discussion

A learning strategy, which is a well-thought-out action plan to accomplish a goal, is an essential component of academic achievement. Metacognition is the practice of students becoming aware of their own learning and mental processes (Farzaneh et. al., 2017). The idea that students should take the lead in their own learning was initially introduced via this method. Because it is in line with personal goals, student motivation is crucial for academic achievement. A person's approach to tasks, with

an emphasis on organizing, carrying out, and assessing work performance and results, is known as their learning strategy. The greatest influence on learning comes from students' metacognitive processes; training them to use these processes may boost performance, foster independence, and help them see how poor methods might impede achievement.

Elaboration strategies are essential for various learning tasks, while organizational strategies are used for basic tasks and complex tasks. Comprehension monitoring strategies check understanding of material, while affective strategies help overcome test anxiety. Learning strategies are crucial in education as they help assess and accommodate individual student learning styles. (Simsek, 2006; Simsek & Balaban, 2010). Learning techniques are deliberate actions taken by students to achieve specific goals. The effectiveness of these strategies is influenced by factors such as the student's capacity, willingness to learn, and perception of their efficacy. Students are required to use specific learning strategies to support autonomous learning and enhance their academic performance. Academic institutions should address cognitive, socio-affective, and motivational aspects of learning. Three primary categories of learning strategies include cognitive techniques, resource regulation techniques, and metacognitive methods. Teachers should provide clear guidance on how to use these strategies, as many students do not acquire them until they are given clear guidance. Elaboration strategies, such as creating analogies, paraphrasing, summarizing, applying new information, and drawing inferences, have the greatest impact on the initial stages of knowledge acquisition (Weinstein and Mayer 1986).

Reference

- Alarcón, A., Alcas, N., Alarcón, H., Natividad, J., and Rodriguez, A. (2019). Use of learning strategies in the university A case study *Propósitos y Representaciones*, 7(1), 10–32.
doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.20511/pyr2019.v7nl.265>
- Rifqi, B. (2017): Students' Learning Strategies for Successfully Studying in Two Majors.

- Bolton, L. (2018). Effective learning strategies to improve basic education outcomes. *K4D Helpdesk Report*. Brighton, UK: Institute of Development Studies.
- Beyaztaş, D.I., D.I and Senemoğlu, N. (2015). Learning Approaches of Successful Students and Factors Affecting Their Learning Approaches. *Education and Science*. Vol. 40, No. 179, 193-216.
- Farzaneh, M., Bagher, G.B., and Manaz, K. (2017). Study and Comparison of Learning Strategies in Successful and Insucessful Students, *International Journal of Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences*, Vo. 2, (1) www.ijahss.com
- Gómez-Puig, M., & Stoyanova, A. (2022). Learning by engaging: Using active learning strategies in higher education. *REIRE Revista d'Innovació i Recerca en Educació*, 15(2), 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.1344/reire.39770>
- Potheroe, N., & Suzanne, C. (2008). Learning strategies are a key to student success. *Principal* (December), v88 n2, p33–37
- Simsek, A., & Balaban, J. (2010). Learning strategies of successful and unsuccessful university students. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 1(1), 36–45, Turkey: Anadolu University.
- Weinstein, Claire, Ridley, D., Dahl, Tove, & Weber, And. (1989). Helping Students Develop Strategies for Effective Learning What are learning strategies?
- Weinstein, C., and Mayer, R. (1986). *The Teaching of Learning Strategies*. Wittrock, M., Ed., *Handbook of Research on Teaching*, Macmillan, New York, 315–327.